

Table I. Major packages of R software used in this study.

Functions	R package
logistic regression analysis	glm
Plot the receiver operating curve (ROC) and measure the area under the ROC (AUC)	pROC
Hosmer and Lemeshow goodness of fit (GOF) test	ResourceSelection
Plot bar diagrams	ggplot2
Plot calibration curves, Brier score and develop nomogram	rms
Decision curve analysis (DCA)	rmda

Table II The baseline characteristics and univariable analysis between ruptured and unruptured group of 700 patients and 1671 aneurysms

Characteristic	Ruptured cohort	Unruptured cohort	P value	Exp	95%CI
Patients					
No.	158(22.6)	542(77.4)			
Female sex	119 (75.3)	356(65.4)	0.023	1.594	1.066-
Age (years)	58.4(12.3)	57.2(10.1)	0.253	1.011	0.994-
< 50	35(22.2)	109(20.1)	0.013	-	-
50-70	95(60.1)	380(70.1)		0.779	0.500-
≥ 70	28(17.7)	53(9.8)		1.645	0.907-
History of SAH	36(22.8)	7(1.3)	<	22.553	9.803-
Number of IAs	2.5(0.9)	2.3(0.7)	0.017	1.277	1.038-
2	202(64.6)	401(74.0)	0.036	-	-
3-4	51(32.3)	134(24.7)		1.496	1.014-
>4	5(3.2)	7(1.3)		2.808	0.873-
Comorbidities					
Hypertension	97 61.4)	271(50.0)	0.012	1.590	1.107-
Diabetes	10 (6.3)	67(12.4)	0.033	0.479	0.240-
	16 (10.1)	58(78.4)	0.836	0.940	0.524-
Heart diseases	10 (6.3)	55(10.1)	0.146	0.598	0.298-
History of stroke	15 (9.5)	63(11.6)	0.454	0.798	0.441-
Smoking	35 (22.2)	95(17.5)	0.188	1.339	0.866-
Drinking	31 (19.6)	75(13.8)	0.074	1.520	0.957-
Aneurysms					
Size, mm	5.7(3.1)	5.2(4.3)	0.214	1.022	0.987-
< 3	22(13.9)	418(27.6)	Ref	-	-
3-7	99(62.7)	808(53.4)	0.773	0.737	0.093-
7-15	34(21.5)	231(15.3)	0.604	1.715	0.223-
15-25	2(1.3)	42(2.8)	0.492	2.061	0.263-

>25	1(0.6)	14(0.9)	0.748	0.660	0.056-
Neck	3.9(1.85)	4.0(2.66)	0.407		
< 3.9	96(60.8)	966(63.8)	0.443	1.141	.0815-
Aspect ratio	1.5(0.82)	1.2(0.66)	<0.001		
>1.5	64(40.5)	291 (19.2)	0.001	2.859	2.030-
Diameter of parent artery	3.3(1.1)	4.0(1.1)	0.001		
< 2	17(10.8)	79(5.2)	0.004	2.189	1.260-
Branching to parent ratio	1.2(0.3)	1.1(0.3)	0.017	1.646	1.088-
>1.2	50(31.6)	273(18.0)	<0.001	2.103	1.467-
Neck to parent ratio	1.3(0.61)	1.2(0.70)	0.090		
>1.2	55(34.8)	463(30.6)	0.276	1.211	0.858-
Size ratio	1.8(0.88)	1.4(1.07)	<0.001	1.299	1.156-
>1.8	63(39.9)	299(19.8)	<0.001	2.653	1.911-
Locations of aneurysms					
Internal carotid artery	84 (53.2)	897(59.3)	Ref	-	-
Posterior	18(11.4)	207(13.7)	0.784	0.929	0.546-
Anterior cerebral artery and branches	13(8.2)	130(8.6)	0.027	1.068	0.579-1.970
Middle cerebral	10(6.3)	128(8.5)	0.796	0.834	0.422-
Posterior circulation	33(12.7)	151(10.8)	<0.001	2.334	1.506-
Location of Posterior circulation	33(20.9)	151(10.0)	<0.001	2.381	1.566-3.620
Geometry					
Regular	70(44.3)	1001(66.2)	Ref	-	-
Irregular	88(55.7)	513(33.8)	<0.001	2.458	1.764-
Parent artery					
Sidewall aneurysm	93(58.9)	1168(77.2)	Ref	-	-
Bifurcation aneurysm	65(41.1)	345(22.8)	<0.001	2.366	1.686-
Inflow angle, mean (SD)	102(29)	108(29)	0.008	1.008	1.002-
>120	83(52.5)	664(43.9)	0.038	1.415	1.019-
Outflow angle	103(29)	101(31)	0.362	1.002	0.997-

>103	84(53.2)	696(46.0)	0.086	1.332	0.959-
Branching angle	130(35)	137(34)	0.017	0.995	0.990-
<130	75 (47.5)	539(35.6)	0.003	1.633	1.174-

Table III. Baseline characteristics of derivation cohort and validation cohort

Characteristic	Derivation Cohort (n=1171)	Validation Cohort (n=500)	P-value
Aneurysm ruptured	104(8.9)	54 (10.8)	220
Female sex	813(69.4)	334(66.8)	0.289
Age (years)	57.9(10.7)	58.0(11.2)	0.785
< 50	237(20.2)	92 (18.4)	0.477
50-70	791(67.5)	338(66.7)	
≥ 70	143(12.2)	70(14.0)	
History of SAH	79(6.7)	34(6.8)	0.968
Number of aneurysms	2.6(1.1)	2.6(1.0)	0.394
2	701(59.9)	308(61.6)	0.796
3-4	417(35.6)	171(34.2)	
>4	53(4.5)	21(4.2)	
Comorbidities			
Hypertension	624 (53.3)	269(53.8)	0.848
Diabetes	136 (11.6)	44(8.8)	0.089
Hypercholesterolemia	121(10.3)	57(11.4)	0.517
Heart diseases	118(10.1)	42(8.4)	0.286
History of stroke	131 (11.2)	60(12.0)	0.632
Smoking	219 (18.7)	99(19.8)	0.601
Drinking	159 (13.6)	84(16.8)	0.087
Size	5.2(4.0)	5.4(4.7)	0.191
< 3	305(26.0)	135(27.0)	0.225
3-7	638(54.5)	269(53.8)	
>7	228(19.5)	96(19.2)	
Neck	4.0(2.6)	4.1(2.6)	0.660
< 3.9	751(64.1)	311(62.2)	0.452
AR	1.21(0.70)	1.23(0.67)	0.580
>1.55	237(20.2)	118 (23.6)	0.124

Diameter of parent artery	3.5(1.1)	3.5 (1.0)	0.974
< 2	71(6.1)	25(5.0)	0.392
Branching to parent ratio	1.2(0.3)	1.1(0.3)	0.297
>1.2	220(18.8)	103(20.6)	0.390
Neck to parent ratio	1.18 (0.70)	1.20(0.73)	0.537
>1.27	366(31.3)	152(30.4)	0.729
Size ratio	1.37(1.02)	1.43(1.15)	0.281
>1.77	246(21.0)	116(23.2)	0.319
Locations of aneurysms			
Internal carotid artery	694 (59.3)	287 (57.4)	0.741
Posterior communicating	150(12.8)	75(15.0)	
Anterior cerebral artery and branches	101(8.6)	42(8.4)	
Middle cerebral artery	94(8.0)	44(8.8)	
PC	132(11.3)	52(10.4)	
Location of PC	132(11.3)	52(10.4)	0.602
Irregular shape	410(35.0)	190(38.0)	0.244
Bifurcation aneurysm	277(23.7)	133(26.6)	0.200
Inflow angle, mean (SD)	97(35)	100(31)	0.064
>120	506(43.2)	241(48.2)	0.420
Outflow angle	102(31)	101(30)	0.660
>103	554(47.3)	226(45.2)	0.429
Branching angle	136(34)	136(35)	0.992
<130	431 (36.8)	183(36.6)	0.936

SAH, subarachnoid hemorrhage; AR, aspect ratio; PC, posterior circulation

Table IV. Baseline characteristics of derivation cohort and validation cohort in subarachnoid hemorrhage patient with multiple aneurysm.

Characteristic	Derivation Cohort (n=271)	Validation Cohort (n=129)	P-value
IA ruptured	113(41.7)	45 (34.9)	0.193
Size			
< 3	73(26.9)	43(33.3)	0.407
3-7	161(59.4)	71(55.0)	
>7	37(13.7)	15(11.6)	
Neck< 3.9 mm	73(26.9)	35(27.1)	0.967
Aspect ratio >1.5	80(29.5)	29(22.5)	0.139
Diameter of parent artery	26(9.6)	14 (10.9)	0.695
Branching to parent ratio >1.2	79(29.2)	28(21.7)	0.116
Neck to parent ratio >1.2	76 (28.0)	36(27.9)	0.977
Size ratio >1.7	68(25.1)	30(23.3)	0.690
Location of Posterior circulation	36(13.3)	22(17.1)	0.317
Irregular shape	112(41.3)	54(41.9)	0.920
Bifurcation aneurysm	100(36.9)	22(32.6)	0.396
Inflow angle >120	139(51.3)	63(48.8)	0.646
Outflow angle >103	136(50.2)	63(48.8)	0.801
Branching angle <130	117(43.2)	61(47.3)	0.439

Figure I Measurements of the aneurysm: dimensions (left) and related angles (right).

Figure II. Calibration curves of the model of MIA patients with SAH in the derivation (A) and validation (B) set.

Figure III. Distribution of aneurysm size(A) and number of combined aneurysms (B) in the ruptured and unruptured aneurysms.

Figure IV. Relationship between mean aneurysm size and irregularities and bifurcation location.